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Attitude Reconstitution Using Splines

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1. Introduction

Piecewise polynomial (or spline) approximation of the attitude angles is a natural and attractive approach to the a posteriori attitude reconstitution problem in case the intermittent (gas jet) control is adopted. In the 'quiet' periods between firings, the main perturbing torque is due to solar radiation pressure. According to MATRA, its magnitude and variation are such that e.g. a third-degree polynomial is expected to represent the attitude to within 0.1 as over several tens of seconds. Even if the useful interval for a fixed polynomial is much shorter than the mean time between firings (which may be 10 minutes), one is free to introduce any number of knot points in the quiet period, at which points the polynomial coefficients are allowed to change according to given continuity conditions. Experience shows that it is better, both with regard to computational efficiency and numerical stability, to subdivide a long interval in this way, than to use a higher-order polynomial. In this note I will show that the spline representation fits naturally into the framework of discrete sequential estimation, and that therefore the Square-Root Information Smoother, for instance, can be applied to its solution.

2. The State Vector

Let $\{t_j\}$ be the knot sequence, i.e. the times at which the polynomial coefficients are allowed to change. All jet firings must occur at these knots, but additional knots may have been inserted in order to reduce the interval lengths when necessary. In the j :th interval, $t_{j-1} < t < t_j$, the attitude angles $u \equiv \alpha_z$, $v \equiv \delta_z$, and $w \equiv \omega$ are approximated by cubic functions,

$$u(t) = u_j(\tau_j) = u_{j0} + u_{j1}\tau_j + u_{j2}\tau_j^2 + u_{j3}\tau_j^3 \quad (1)$$

etc, where

$$\tau_j = t - \frac{1}{2}(t_{j-1} + t_j) \quad (2)$$

is the time measured from the centre of the interval. Thus, the attitude is completely specified by the knot sequence $\{t_j\}$ and the twelve coefficients u_{jk}, v_{jk}, w_{jk} ($k = 0, \dots, 3$) per interval.

The state vector $\underline{s}_j$ must contain all variables to be estimated relevant to interval j . This means the twelve coefficients above (in some form), but also the gyro drift rates (one scalar per gyro), and possibly still some instrument parameter(s). Since the polynomial coefficients for u, v, w usually enter the observation equations non-linearly, it is necessary to linearize the functions (1) about some reference values $\tilde{u}_{jk}, \tilde{v}_{jk}, \tilde{w}_{jk}$. In view of the fact that the satellite, to a first approximation, spins uniformly about a fixed axis, a natural choice for the reference motion is

$$\tilde{u}_{j0} = \langle \tilde{\alpha}_z \rangle_j, \quad \tilde{u}_{j1} = \tilde{u}_{j2} = \tilde{u}_{j3} = 0 \quad (3a)$$

$$\tilde{v}_{j0} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_z \rangle_j, \quad \tilde{v}_{j1} = \tilde{v}_{j2} = \tilde{v}_{j3} = 0 \quad (3b)$$

$$\tilde{w}_{j0} = \langle \tilde{\omega} \rangle_j, \quad \tilde{w}_{j1} = \Omega_j, \quad \tilde{w}_{j2} = \tilde{w}_{j3} = 0 \quad (3c)$$

where $\langle \rangle_j$ denotes an average over the interval $t_{j-1} < t < t_j$, $\tilde{\alpha}_z, \tilde{\delta}_z, \tilde{\omega}$ are the a priori attitude angles (accurate to a few as only), and Ω_j is the approximate spin rate during the interval. Since it is not certain that this particular choice is good enough, we shall not use it in the following, except when explicitly stated.

Let $b_{j1}, b_{j2}, \dots, b_{jn}$ be the average gyro drift rates during the interval ($n = \text{number of gyros}$). The state vector is then the $(12+n)$ -vector

$$\underline{s}_j = (u_{j0} \tilde{u}_{j0} \quad u_{j1} \tilde{u}_{j1} \quad \dots \quad w_{j3} \tilde{w}_{j3} \quad b_{j1} \quad b_{j2} \quad \dots \quad b_{jn})' \quad (4)$$

3. The Transition Equation

At the knot t_j , the functions $u(t), v(t), w(t)$ and their derivatives must satisfy certain continuity conditions. With

$$T_j = \frac{1}{2}(t_j - t_{j-1}) \quad (5)$$

denoting half the interval length, we have

$$u_{j+1}(-T_{j+1}) = u_j(T_j) + U_{j0} \quad (6a)$$

$$\dot{u}_{j+1}(-T_{j+1}) = \dot{u}_j(T_j) + U_{j1} \quad (6b)$$

$$\ddot{u}_{j+1}(-T_{j+1}) = \ddot{u}_j(T_j) + U_{j2} \quad (6c)$$

$$\dddot{u}_{j+1}(-T_{j+1}) = \dddot{u}_j(T_j) + U_{j3} \quad (6d)$$

etc, where U_{jk} , V_{jk} , W_{jk} are stochastic variables with known expectation and covariance. In particular, if t_j is an auxiliary knot, i.e. one not associated with a jet firing, we require that $u(t)$ is twice continuously differentiable. Hence $U_{j0} = U_{j1} = U_{j2} = 0$, while the third derivative is allowed to jump ($U_{j3} \neq 0$). In this case the expectation $E(U_{jk}) = 0$ for all k ; the variances are also zero for $k < 3$ but finite for $k = 3$. At a jet knot other conditions apply; in particular we will have $U_{j1} \neq 0$.

Inserting the cubic functions into the continuity conditions (6), we can solve for the state variables in the $(j+1)$:th interval ($\Delta u_{j+1,k} \equiv u_{j+1,k} - \tilde{u}_{j+1,k}$, etc) in terms of their values in the j :th interval. Consider for simplicity only the first four variables, and introduce the vectors

$$\underline{u}_j \equiv (u_{j0} \quad u_{j1} \quad u_{j2} \quad u_{j3})' \quad (7a)$$

$$\tilde{\underline{u}}_j \equiv (\tilde{u}_{j0} \quad \tilde{u}_{j1} \quad \tilde{u}_{j2} \quad \tilde{u}_{j3})' \quad (7b)$$

$$\underline{U}_j \equiv (U_{j0} \quad U_{j1} \quad U_{j2} \quad U_{j3})' \quad (7c)$$

For the state sub-vector $\Delta \underline{u}_j \equiv \underline{u}_j - \tilde{\underline{u}}_j$ we then find the transition equation

$$\Delta \underline{u}_{j+1} = \underline{A}_j \Delta \underline{u}_j + \underline{A}_j \tilde{\underline{u}}_j - \tilde{\underline{u}}_{j+1} + \underline{B}_j \underline{U}_j \quad (8)$$

where

$$\underline{A}_j \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 1 & (T_j + T_{j+1}) & (T_j + T_{j+1})^2 & (T_j + T_{j+1})^3 \\ 0 & 1 & 2(T_j + T_{j+1}) & 3(T_j + T_{j+1})^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 3(T_j + T_{j+1}) \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\underline{B}_j = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & T_{j+1} & \frac{1}{2} T_{j+1}^2 & \frac{1}{6} T_{j+1}^3 \\ 0 & 1 & T_{j+1} & \frac{1}{2} T_{j+1}^2 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} T_{j+1} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{6} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Note that the last three terms in (8) form a vector whose expectation and covariance can be computed.

For the gyro drift rates, the state sub-vector $\underline{b}_j = (b_{j1} \dots b_{jn})'$, a Markov model similar to (A.8.4) is adopted,

$$\underline{b}_{j+1} = \underline{M}_j \underline{b}_j + \underline{n}_{bj} \quad (11)$$

with

$$\underline{M}_j = \exp[-(T_j + T_{j+1})/\tau_b] \underline{I}_n \quad (12)$$

$$E(\underline{n}_{bj}) = \underline{0}_n \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Cov}(\underline{n}_{bj}) = [2\sigma_b^2(T_j + T_{j+1})/\tau_b] \underline{I}_n \quad (14)$$

τ_b is the time constant and σ_b the standard deviation of the drift rates.

The transition equation for the full state vector thus becomes

$$\underline{s}_{j+1} = \underline{\Phi}_j \underline{s}_j + \underline{q}_j \quad (15)$$

where

$$\underline{\Phi}_j = \text{diag}\{\underline{A}_j \quad \underline{A}_j \quad \underline{A}_j \quad \underline{M}_j\} \quad (16)$$

$$\underline{q}_j = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{A}_j \underline{u}_j - \underline{u}_{j+1} + \underline{B}_j \underline{U}_j \\ \underline{A}_j \underline{v}_j - \underline{v}_{j+1} + \underline{B}_j \underline{V}_j \\ \underline{A}_j \underline{w}_j - \underline{w}_{j+1} + \underline{B}_j \underline{W}_j \\ \underline{n}_{bj} \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

In order to obtain the transition equation (15) in the form (A.B.1) - (A.B.2) as required for the Square-Root Information Smoother, we need the expectation and covariance of $\underline{q}_j$. Then we can introduce a process noise vector $\underline{n}_{pj}$ such that

$$\underline{q}_j = \text{Cov}(\underline{q}_j)^{\frac{1}{2}} \underline{n}_{pj} \quad (18)$$

The properties of this vector are

$$E(\underline{n}_{pj}) = \text{Cov}(\underline{q}_j)^{-\frac{1}{2}} E(\underline{q}_j) \quad (19)$$

$$\text{Cov}(\underline{n}_{pj}) = \underline{I}_{12+n} \quad (20)$$

The expectation of $\underline{q}_j$ is

$$E(\underline{q}_j) = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{A}_j \underline{\tilde{u}}_j - \underline{\tilde{u}}_{j+1} + \underline{B}_j E(\underline{U}_j) \\ \underline{A}_j \underline{\tilde{v}}_j - \underline{\tilde{v}}_{j+1} + \underline{B}_j E(\underline{V}_j) \\ \underline{A}_j \underline{\tilde{w}}_j - \underline{\tilde{w}}_{j+1} + \underline{B}_j E(\underline{W}_j) \\ \underline{0}_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (21)$$

where, for an auxiliary knot,

$$E(\underline{U}_j) = E(\underline{V}_j) = E(\underline{W}_j) = \underline{0}_4 \quad (22)$$

For a jet knot we know the (intended) change in angular momentum due to the thrust, expressed in body coordinates ($\underline{T}$); thus we have a non-zero expectation of $\Delta(\underline{T}'\underline{\omega})$. From (A.3.4) - (A.3.5) we then have

$$E \begin{pmatrix} \underline{U}_{j1} \\ \underline{V}_{j1} \\ \underline{W}_{j1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sec(v)\sin(w) & \sec(v)\cos(w) & 0 \\ -\cos(w) & \sin(w) & 0 \\ -\tan(v)\sin(w) & -\tan(v)\cos(w) & 1 \end{pmatrix} E[\Delta(\underline{T}'\underline{\omega})] \quad (23)$$

where v and w should of course refer to time t_j ; for the remaining components

we have

$$E(U_{jk}) = E(V_{jk}) = E(W_{jk}) = 0, \quad k = 0, 2, 3 \quad (\text{jet knot}) \quad (24)$$

As shown by (18) - (19) we also need some a priori estimate of $\text{Cov}(q_j)$ in order to perform the attitude reconstitution. Although this should not be very critical (it has a function similar to the weights in a conventional least-squares solution), one should still be careful and in particular try to modelise any strong correlation that can be foreseen. We can assume that the gyro drift rates are uncorrelated with external perturbations, so we only have to consider correlations among the stochastic components of $\underline{U}$, $\underline{V}$, and $\underline{W}$. Such correlations will exist even if the perturbations about the telescope axes are uncorrelated. Lacking a more detailed model, this seems to be a reasonable hypothesis since these axes nearly coincide with the principal axes of inertia. If furthermore the perturbations are of similar magnitude about the different axes, we find (dropping subscript j)

$$\text{Cov} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{U} \\ \underline{V} \\ \underline{W} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{S} \sec^2(v) & \underline{0} & -\underline{S} \sec^2(v) \sin(v) \\ \underline{0} & \underline{S} & \underline{0} \\ -\underline{S} \sec^2(v) \sin(v) & \underline{0} & \underline{S} \sec^2(v) \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

where $\underline{S}$ is the covariance of the components X_{jk} , $k = 0, \dots, 3$ (for $X = U, V, W$), expressed as true arcs on the sky. The trigonometric factors in (25) are obtained by squaring the (3,3)-matrix in (23). Note that there is a correlation between e.g. U_{j1} and W_{j1} amounting to $-\sin(v)$, cf. the definition of $\overline{\Delta\omega} = \Delta u \cdot \sin(v) + \Delta w$. The upper-triangular Cholesky square root of (25) is readily obtained, and since $\underline{B}_j$ are already upper-triangular, we get

$$\text{Cov}(q_j)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{B}_j \underline{S}_{-j}^{\frac{1}{2}} & \underline{0} & -\underline{B}_j \underline{S}_{-j}^{\frac{1}{2}} \tan(v) & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{B}_j \underline{S}_{-j}^{\frac{1}{2}} & \underline{0} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \underline{B}_j \underline{S}_{-j}^{\frac{1}{2}} \sec(v) & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \text{Cov}(n_{-bj})^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (26)$$

For an auxiliary knot we take

$$\underline{S}_j = \text{diag}\{0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad S_3\} \quad (27)$$

where S_3 is the a priori variance of $U_{j3} \cos(v)$, V_{j3} , and $W_{j3} + U_{j3} \sin(v)$. S_3 should rather be chosen too large than too small. Indeed, in normal cubic spline fitting techniques, the jumps of the third derivative are usually unconstrained, which corresponds to $S_3 = \infty$. Using a finite S_3 means that a certain degree of continuity is imposed also on the third derivative, which limits the 'flexibility' of the spline. In the extreme case of $S_3 = 0$, the knot is effectively removed, since the polynomial is then the same on either side of t_j .

For a jet knot we may take

$$\underline{S}_j = \text{diag}\{S_0 \quad S_1 \quad S_2 \quad S_3\} \quad (28)$$

where S_3 may be the same as in (27) while S_1 depends on the uncertainty of $\Delta(\underline{T}'\underline{\omega})$ due to the firing. S_0 and S_2 should also be non-zero because of the finite duration of the thrust and timing uncertainty (Fig. 1). Again, it is better to make the S_k 's too large; $S_k = \infty$ would mean that the splines before and after t_j are treated as statistically independent.

Fig. 1. Apparent discontinuity (U_{j0}) due to timing error and finite thrust interval.

4. Gyro Observation Equations

The n ($= 4?$) gyros sense the instantaneous rotation vector in body coordinates $\underline{\omega} = (\omega_x \ \omega_y \ \omega_z)'$. Compared to the knot frequency, the sampling frequency of the gyros is so high that we can regard the gyro signal as a continuous function of time, $\underline{g}(t)$, where $\underline{g}$ is an n -vector. With the usual gyro model, (A.8.2) - (A.8.7), we have

$$\underline{g}(t) = \underline{K} \underline{T}' \underline{\omega}(t) + \underline{b}(t) + \underline{v}(t) \quad (29)$$

Here, $\underline{K}$ is the $(n,3)$ -matrix specifying the orientation and sensitivity of each gyro, $\underline{b}(t)$ is the gyro drift rates, and $\underline{v}(t)$ high-frequency noise. We shall assume that the time constant for the variations of $\underline{b}(t)$ is much longer than the knot intervals $(2T_j)$, so that $\underline{b}(t) \approx \underline{b}_j$ for $t_{j-1} < t < t_j$, and that the correlation length of $\underline{v}(t)$ is much shorter than the knot intervals, so that this component from our point of view can be regarded as white noise.

In principle one can write down one observation equation for each gyro sample. But since we only have 4-5 state variables per gyro to estimate in each knot interval, the processing of perhaps hundreds of data points per gyro would be very inefficient. In view of the local attitude model (third-degree polynomial), it appears that the first three centred moments (order 0, 1, 2) of the gyro signal provide sufficient statistic. Thus, the average spin rate, average acceleration, etc, can be taken as 'observations' instead of the actual gyro samples. Defining the moments

$$\underline{m}_{jk} = \frac{1}{2T_j} \int_{-T_j}^{T_j} \underline{g}[\frac{1}{2}(t_{j-1} + t_j) + \tau_j] \tau_j^k d\tau_j, \quad k = 0, 1, 2 \quad (30)$$

and using $E(\underline{b}) = E(\underline{v}) = \underline{0}$, we find

$$E(\underline{m}_{jk}) = \underline{K} \frac{1}{2T_j} \int_{-T_j}^{T_j} \underline{T}' \underline{\omega} \tau_j^k d\tau_j + \begin{cases} \underline{b}_j & \text{for } k = 0 \\ \underline{0} & \text{for } k = 1 \\ \underline{b}_j T_j^2 / 3 & \text{for } k = 2 \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

Since the observation equations require the partial derivatives of $E(\underline{m}_{jk})$ with respect to the state variables, we presently evaluate the integral in (31) in terms of the spline coefficients.

Dropping subscript j , we have from (A.3.4),

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_x &= \dot{u} \cos(v) \sin(w) - \dot{v} \cos(w) \\ \omega_y &= \dot{u} \cos(v) \cos(w) + \dot{v} \sin(w) \\ \omega_z &= \dot{u} \sin(v) + \dot{w}\end{aligned}\quad (32)$$

The first derivatives $\dot{u}$, $\dot{v}$, $\dot{w}$ are obtained directly from (1) to $O(\tau^3)$. For the trigonometric functions in (32) we use the series expansions

$$\begin{aligned}\sin(x_0 + x_1\tau + x_2\tau^2 + x_3\tau^3) &= \sin(x_0) + \tau x_1 \cos(x_0) - \tau^2 [\frac{1}{2}x_1^2 \sin(x_0) - x_2 \cos(x_0)] + O(\tau^3) \\ \cos(x_0 + x_1\tau + x_2\tau^2 + x_3\tau^3) &= \cos(x_0) - \tau x_1 \sin(x_0) - \tau^2 [\frac{1}{2}x_1^2 \cos(x_0) + x_2 \sin(x_0)] + O(\tau^3) \\ &\dots\end{aligned}\quad (33)$$

(with $x = v, w$) to get the angular velocity components in the form

$$\omega_x(\tau) = \omega_{x0} + \omega_{x1}\tau + \omega_{x2}\tau^2 + O(\tau^3) \quad (34)$$

etc. After a short calculation we find

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_{z0} &= w_1 + u_1 \sin(v_0) \\ \omega_{z1} &= 2w_2 + u_1 v_1 \cos(v_0) + 2u_2 \sin(v_0) \\ \omega_{z2} &= 3w_3 + (u_1 v_2 + 2u_2 v_1) \cos(v_0) - (\frac{1}{2}u_1 v_1^2 - 3u_3) \sin(v_0)\end{aligned}\quad (35)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}\omega_{x0} &= A_0 \cos(w_0) + B_0 \sin(w_0), & \omega_{y0} &= B_0 \cos(w_0) - A_0 \sin(w_0) \\ \omega_{x1} &= A_1 \cos(w_0) + B_1 \sin(w_0), & \omega_{y1} &= B_1 \cos(w_0) - A_1 \sin(w_0) \\ \omega_{x2} &= A_2 \cos(w_0) + B_2 \sin(w_0), & \omega_{y2} &= B_2 \cos(w_0) - A_1 \sin(w_0)\end{aligned}\quad (36)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}A_0 &= -v_1 \\ A_1 &= u_1 w_1 \cos(v_0) - 2v_2 \\ A_2 &= \frac{1}{2}v_1 w_1^2 - 3v_3 + (u_1 w_2 + 2u_2 w_1) \cos(v_0) - u_1 v_1 w_1 \sin(v_0)\end{aligned}\quad (37)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_0 &= u_1 \cos(v_0) \\
 B_1 &= v_1 w_1 + 2u_2 \cos(v_0) - u_1 v_1 \sin(v_0) \\
 B_2 &= v_1 w_2 + 2v_2 w_1 + [3u_3 - \frac{1}{2}u_1(v_1^2 + w_1^2)] \cos(v_0) - (u_1 v_2 + 2u_2 v_1) \sin(v_0)
 \end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

From the power series expansions (34) we now obtain the moments of $\underline{T}'\underline{\omega}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu_{x0} &\equiv (2T)^{-1} \int_{-T}^T \omega_x(\tau) d\tau = \omega_{x0} + \frac{T^2}{3} \omega_{x2} + O(T^4) \\
 \mu_{x1} &\equiv (2T)^{-1} \int_{-T}^T \omega_x(\tau) \tau d\tau = \frac{T^2}{3} \omega_{x1} + O(T^4) \\
 \mu_{x2} &\equiv (2T)^{-1} \int_{-T}^T \omega_x(\tau) \tau^2 d\tau = \frac{T^2}{3} \omega_{x0} + \frac{T^4}{5} \omega_{x2} + O(T^6)
 \end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

etc. From these we construct the 9-vector $\underline{\mu} \equiv (\mu_{x0} \ \mu_{y0} \ \mu_{z0} \ \mu_{x1} \ \dots \ \mu_{z2})'$ and the $(9, 12+n)$ -matrix $\underline{H} \equiv \partial \underline{\mu} / \partial \underline{s}$ of partial derivatives with respect to the spline coefficients (and $\underline{b}$). From (31) we then have

$$\underline{P} \equiv \frac{\partial E(\underline{m})}{\partial \underline{s}} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{K} & \underline{0} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{K} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \underline{K} \end{pmatrix} \underline{H} + \begin{pmatrix} & & \underline{I}_n \\ \underline{0}(3n, 12) & \underline{0}(n, n) & \\ & & \frac{1}{3} T^2 \underline{I}_n \end{pmatrix} \tag{40}$$

where $\underline{m} \equiv (\underline{m}_{j0} \ \underline{m}_{j1} \ \underline{m}_{j2})'$.

If $\underline{\tilde{m}}_j$ is the vector of gyro signal moments computed with the reference attitude parameters $\underline{\tilde{u}}, \underline{\tilde{v}}, \underline{\tilde{w}}$, we get the gyro observation equation

$$\underline{P}_j \underline{s}_j = \underline{m}_j - \underline{\tilde{m}}_j + \underline{v}_m \tag{41}$$

where $\underline{m}_j$ are the observed moments and $\underline{v}_m$ is a noise vector. A normalised observation equation (with unit covariance noise) results from pre-multiplying (41) with $\text{Cov}(\underline{v}_m)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$. Assuming that the correlation time of the gyro noise

is short compared to the interval length, $\tau_v \ll 2T_j$, we find

$$\text{Cov}(\underline{v}_m)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{3}{2} \underline{I}_n & \underline{0} & -\frac{5}{2} T^{-2} \underline{I}_n \\ \underline{0} & \sqrt{3} T^{-1} \underline{I}_n & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \sqrt{5} T^{-2} \underline{I}_n \end{pmatrix} (T/\tau_v)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sigma_v^{-1} \quad (42)$$

Here, σ_v is the standard deviation of the high-frequency noise.

The general expression for $\underline{H} \equiv \partial \underline{\mu} / \partial \underline{s}$ is rather bulky and shall not be given here. It must of course be evaluated with the reference attitude parameters $\tilde{u}_{jk}, \tilde{v}_{jk}, \tilde{w}_{jk}$. With the particular reference attitude (3) it reduces however to the simple form shown in Fig. 2 (next page). In this case $\underline{\lambda}' \underline{\Omega} = (0 \ 0 \ \Omega)'$, so that

$$\underline{\lambda}' \underline{\Omega} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{K} & \underline{0} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{K} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \underline{K} \end{pmatrix} (0 \ 0 \ \Omega \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ \frac{T^2 \Omega}{3})' \quad (43)$$

5. Star Mapper Observation Equation

The equation resulting from the timing (τ) of a star mapper transit in the j :th interval $t_{j-1} < t < t_j$ is found by a trivial modification of (A.9.15) - (A.9.18). Let $(\tilde{\eta} \ \tilde{\zeta})$ be the field coordinates of the star at the observed transit time, as computed from its Catalogue position and the reference attitude $\tilde{u}, \tilde{v}, \tilde{w}$. Also, let $\tilde{\eta}_f(\zeta)$ be the known equation of the central star mapper slit, and $\tilde{\eta}'_f(\zeta) \equiv (d/d\zeta)\tilde{\eta}_f(\zeta)$. Because of attitude and position errors, the computed field coordinates will in general not satisfy $\tilde{\eta} = \tilde{\eta}_f(\tilde{\zeta})$, and the difference will be used as the right-hand side of the observation equation. Using (A.9.17) and (A.9.3) we get

$$\underline{B}_f(\tilde{\zeta}) \underline{D}_j(\tau) \begin{pmatrix} \Delta u(\tau) \\ \Delta v(\tau) \\ \Delta w(\tau) \end{pmatrix} = \tilde{\eta}'_f(\tilde{\zeta}) - \tilde{\eta} \quad (44)$$

where $\underline{B}_f(\zeta)$ is given by (A.9.18),

$\underline{H} \setminus \underline{s}$	Δu_0	Δu_1	Δu_2	Δu_3	Δv_0	Δv_1	Δv_2	Δv_3	Δw_0	Δw_1	Δw_2	Δw_3	b
H_{x0}	0	$(1 - \frac{T^2 \Omega^2}{6}) cv sw$	$\frac{2T^2 \Omega}{3} cv cv$	$T^2 cv sw$	0	$-(1 - \frac{T^2 \Omega^2}{6}) cv$	$\frac{2T^2 \Omega}{3} sv$	$-T^2 cw$	0	0	0	0	0 ... 0
H_{y0}	0	$(1 - \frac{T^2 \Omega^2}{6}) cv cv$	$-\frac{2T^2 \Omega}{3} cv sv$	$T^2 cv cv$	0	$(1 - \frac{T^2 \Omega^2}{6}) sv$	$\frac{2T^2 \Omega}{3} cv$	$T^2 sv$	0	0	0	0	0 ... 0
H_{z0}	0	sv	0	$T^2 sv$	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0 ... 0
H_{x1}	0	$\frac{T^2 \Omega}{3} cv cv$	$\frac{2T^2}{3} cv sv$	0	0	$\frac{T^2 \Omega}{3} sv$	$-\frac{2T^2}{3} cv$	0	0	0	0	0	0 ... 0
H_{y1}	0	$-\frac{T^2 \Omega}{3} cv sv$	$\frac{2T^2}{3} cv cv$	0	0	$\frac{T^2 \Omega}{3} cv$	$\frac{2T^2}{3} sv$	0	0	0	0	0	0 ... 0
H_{z1}	0	0	$\frac{2T^2}{3} sv$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{2T^2}{3}$	0	0 ... 0
H_{x2}	0	$(\frac{T^2}{3} - \frac{T^4 \Omega^2}{10}) cv sv$	$\frac{2T^4 \Omega}{5} cv cv$	$\frac{3T^4}{5} cv sv$	0	$-(\frac{T^2}{3} - \frac{T^4 \Omega^2}{10}) cv$	$\frac{2T^4 \Omega}{5} sv$	$-\frac{3T^4}{5} cw$	0	0	0	0	0 ... 0
H_{y2}	0	$(\frac{T^2}{3} - \frac{T^4 \Omega^2}{10}) cv cv$	$-\frac{2T^4 \Omega}{5} cv sv$	$\frac{3T^4}{5} cv cv$	0	$(\frac{T^2}{3} - \frac{T^4 \Omega^2}{10}) sv$	$\frac{2T^4 \Omega}{5} cv$	$\frac{3T^4}{5} sv$	0	0	0	0	0 ... 0
H_{z2}	0	$\frac{T^2}{3} sv$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{T^2}{3}$	0	$\frac{3T^4}{5}$	0 ... 0

Fig. 2. The partial derivatives matrix $\underline{H} \equiv \partial \underline{y} / \partial \underline{s}$ evaluated with the reference attitude parameters (3).

$T = T_j, \quad \Omega = \Omega_j = \tilde{w}_{j1}, \quad cv = \cos(\tilde{v}_{j0}), \quad sv = \sin(\tilde{v}_{j0}), \quad cw = \cos(\tilde{w}_{j0}), \quad sw = \sin(\tilde{w}_{j0})$

$$\underline{D}_j(\tau) \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \cos[v_j(\tau)]\sin[w_j(\tau)] & -\cos[w_j(\tau)] & 0 \\ \cos[v_j(\tau)]\cos[w_j(\tau)] & \sin[w_j(\tau)] & 0 \\ \sin[v_j(\tau)] & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (45)$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} \Delta u(\tau) \\ \Delta v(\tau) \\ \Delta w(\tau) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \tau & \tau^2 & \tau^3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \tau & \tau^2 & \tau^3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \tau & \tau^2 & \tau^3 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix} \underline{s}_j \quad (46)$$

Multiplying (44) with $(\sigma_p^2 + \Omega^2 \sigma_\tau^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, where σ_p and σ_τ are the positional and timing mean errors, gives the observation equation in normalized form.

6. Inclusion of IDT Data (Second Pass)

It has been found that a fairly accurate attitude about the z axis is needed for eliminating slit inconsistencies in the set solution. The maximum peak-to-peak error should if possible be less than 0.5 grid period or 0.6 as. It may be that this can actually be obtained with the improved attitude reconstitution enabled by the gas jets, as described above. If this is not the case there is however still the option to include IDT data in the attitude determination. Since these provide extremely accurate information precisely on the rotation about the z axis, this should certainly do the trick. The required modification of the data processing are as follows.

In a first pass of the attitude reconstitution, only gyro and Star Mapper data are used as outlined in the previous sections. This will give a first pass attitude which is sufficient for executing the IDT preprocessing. Only a limited time interval is taken, e.g. corresponding to a set, so that a lot of intermediate results can be saved conveniently, e.g. all transition equations, gyro and Star Mapper observation equations. The IDT preprocessing gives phase errors ($\hat{\beta}_3$) for the different stars of each frame, referred to the first pass attitude. If we follow a star through successive frames, as it traverses the FOV, we obtain by least-squares regression versus time an estimate of $d\hat{\beta}_3/dt$. This gives information about the angular velocity error about the z axis and can therefore be utilized in the second pass to improve the attitude about the z axis. The second pass of the attitude reconstitution takes advantage of the saved results from the first pass in order to reduce

the amount of computing.

Let $a \equiv \partial G / \partial \eta$, $b \equiv \partial G / \partial \zeta$ be a priori 'scale values' in the two field coordinates, and define a scale correction c such that $(1+c)a$ is the correct average longitudinal scale. We shall now derive the IDT observation equation in exactly the same form as a gyro equation, with c corresponding to the gyro drift rate. If $\dot{G}$ is the actual time derivative of a star's grid coordinate, and $\tilde{G}$ the derivative expected according to the first-pass attitude, we have

$$\dot{G} - \tilde{G} = \frac{1}{2\pi} d\hat{\beta}_3/dt \quad (47)$$

Hence, from the linear regression of $\hat{\beta}_3$ versus time, we have an estimate of $\dot{G} - \tilde{G}$ for some instant τ (the mid-point of the regression interval). But

$$\tilde{G} = a \tilde{\eta} + b \tilde{\zeta} \quad (48)$$

if the single tilde ($\tilde{\quad}$) marks values derived from the first-pass attitude; while the true rates are related as

$$\dot{G} = (1+c)a \dot{\eta} + b \dot{\zeta} \quad (49)$$

(The transverse scale error is neglected.) Using that $\dot{\eta} \approx -\Omega$, we find

$$\frac{1}{a}(\dot{G} - \tilde{G}) = (\dot{\eta} - \tilde{\dot{\eta}}) + (b/a)(\dot{\zeta} - \tilde{\dot{\zeta}}) - \Omega c \quad (50)$$

From (A.9.15) we have however, for $\eta \approx 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\eta} &= \tan \zeta \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} \omega_x \mp \tan \zeta \sin \frac{\gamma}{2} \omega_y - \omega_z \\ \dot{\zeta} &= \mp \sin \frac{\gamma}{2} \omega_x + \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} \omega_y \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

and similarly for $\tilde{\dot{\eta}}$, $\tilde{\dot{\zeta}}$ in terms of $\tilde{\omega}_x$, $\tilde{\omega}_y$, $\tilde{\omega}_z$. Thus (50) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{a}(\dot{G} - \tilde{G}) &= (\tan \zeta \cos \frac{\gamma}{2} \mp \frac{b}{a} \sin \frac{\gamma}{2})(\omega_x - \tilde{\omega}_x) \\ &\quad + (\mp \tan \zeta \sin \frac{\gamma}{2} + \frac{b}{a} \cos \frac{\gamma}{2})(\omega_y - \tilde{\omega}_y) - (\omega_z - \tilde{\omega}_z) - \Omega c \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

If the IDT data are only used to improve the rotation about the z axis, we may put $(\omega_x - \tilde{\omega}_x) = (\omega_y - \tilde{\omega}_y) = 0$, and (52) can now be written

$$(\omega_z - \tilde{\omega}_z) + \Omega c = (\tilde{\omega}_z - \tilde{\tilde{\omega}}_z) - \frac{1}{a}(\dot{G} - \tilde{G}) \quad (53)$$

which is an observation equation for $\Delta\omega_z \equiv \omega_z - \tilde{\omega}_z$ and c at time τ . This is however still not in the required gyro moments equation form (41).

If we regard the IDT data as resulting from the $(n+1)$:th gyro, with input axis parallel to the telescope z axis and unit sensitivity, the last row in the $(n+1,3)$ -matrix $\underline{K}$ is $(0 \ 0 \ 1)$. According to (31) and (39), the centred moments in the interval $t_{j-1} < t < t_j$ (or $-T < \tau < T$) are

$$\begin{aligned} E(m_{j0}) &= \omega_{z0} + \frac{T^2}{3} \omega_{z2} + \Omega c \\ E(m_{j1}) &= \frac{T^2}{3} \omega_{z1} \\ E(m_{j2}) &= \frac{T^2}{3} \omega_{z0} + \frac{T^4}{5} \omega_{z2} + \frac{T^2}{3} \Omega c \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

Inverting, we find that the polynomial for ω_z in the interval can be written

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_z(\tau) &= \omega_{z0} + \omega_{z1}\tau + \omega_{z2}\tau^2 = \\ &= \frac{3}{4}(3 - 5\tau^2/T^2) m_{j0} + (3\tau/T^2) m_{j1} - (15/4T^2)(1 - 3\tau^2/T^2) m_{j2} - \Omega c \\ &= e_{j0}(\tau) m_{j0} + e_{j1}(\tau) m_{j1} + e_{j2}(\tau) m_{j2} - \Omega c \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

When this is inserted in (53) we obtain an observation equation for $m_{jk} - \tilde{\tilde{m}}_{jk}$:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{j0}(\tau)(m_{j0} - \tilde{\tilde{m}}_{j0}) + e_{j1}(\tau)(m_{j1} - \tilde{\tilde{m}}_{j1}) + e_{j2}(\tau)(m_{j2} - \tilde{\tilde{m}}_{j2}) = \\ = \tilde{\omega}_z(\tau) - \tilde{\tilde{\omega}}_z(\tau) - \frac{1}{a}(\dot{G} - \tilde{G})(\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

If $(\dot{G} - \tilde{G})(\tau)$ is determined for several instances τ in the interval $[-T_j, T_j]$, we can use (56) to make a least-squares determination of $m_{jk} - \tilde{\tilde{m}}_{jk}$, $k = 0, 1, 2$. This gives also the covariance of the moments. This solution is then inserted in (41) as a gyro observation.

Since c is constant and the variation of Ω should be small, we may put $b_{j,n+1} = \Omega c$, with infinite time constant in the transition equation.